

effect between photoperiod and temperature could be adapted to wider areas because a high temperature can complement the insufficiency of

photoperiod in low latitudes and a longer photoperiod can complement the inefficiency of temperature in high latitudes. The ideal type of sterile line for

hybrid rice production has a low CFP, a high CSP, a wide TRPS, and a high intensity of supplementary effect between light and temperature. □

The relationship of photosensitivity and sterility in photosensitive genic male sterile (PGMS) lines

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PGMS rice was first discovered in a field of Nongken 58S, a photoperiod-sensitive japonica variety. Photoperiod controls both the development and the pollen fertility of Nongken 58S. Most PGMS lines were photoperiod-sensitive; photoperiod-insensitive sterile lines derived from Nongken 58S became thermosensitive sterile lines. We wanted to breed PGMS lines that are photoperiod insensitive to flowering induction.

We crossed Mudanjiang 8, a photoperiod-insensitive variety, with Nongken 58S. We selected sterile plants with short growth durations from the F₂. From the F₉, we selected the sterile line E85S. We planted it and its parents in 1990 under short day (SD) 10 h light/d, and long day (LD) 14.5 h light/d conditions to observe growth duration and pollen fertility percent (see table).

E85S is insensitive to photoperiod for flowering induction as is Mudanjiang 8, and is sensitive to photoperiod in its fertility alteration, like Nongken 58S. These results indicate that different genes control photosensitive sterility and photosensitive flowering induction and they can be recombined in new types of PGMS lines. □

Fertility and photosensitivity of E85S and its parents. China, 1991.

	Nongken 58S	Mudanjiang 8	E85S
SD heading promotion rate ^a	38.5	-3.4	2.0
Photoperiod sensitivity	Strong	Weak	Weak
Days from sowing to heading with at least 14.5 h of light/d	104	59	58
Maturity type	Late	Early	Early
Fertile pollen (%)			
In SD	70.2	77.4	65.6
In LD	0.0	76.8	0.0

$$^a\text{SD heading promotion rate} = \frac{d \text{ from sowing to heading in LD} - d \text{ from sowing to heading in SD}}{d \text{ from sowing to heading in LD}} \times 100.$$

Identification of CMS lines for hybrid rice development under northern Indian conditions

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We evaluated 13 cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines for adaptability and stability for pollen sterility under the subhumid tropical conditions of western UP in northern India. V20 A, which originated from China, and IR62829 A and IR58025 A, which originated from IRRI, were obtained from the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad. PMS-1 through PMS-10 originated from Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Kapurthala. We planted 5-row plots of each line on 16 Jul 1991 under strict isolation, using *Sesbania* spp. as a physical barrier. Data were recorded for

Performance of CMS lines at Pantnagar, India, during 1991 wet season.

CMS line	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Pollen sterility (%)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Stability
V20 A	81	72.6	100.0	100.0	Stable
IR62829 A	93	71.7	99.7	99.1	Needs purification
IR58025 A	99	81.0	100.0	99.9	Stable
PMS-1	109	64.1	100.0	100.0	Stable
PMS-2	102	63.6	100.0	99.7	Stable
PMS-3	109	70.8	98.4	99.9	Unstable
PMS-4	113	64.8	99.4	99.9	Needs purification
PMS-5	113	66.0	100.0	100.0	Stable
PMS-6	114	66.2	98.1	100.0	Unstable
PMS-7	109	74.6	95.1	100.0	Unstable
PMS-8	109	64.4	100.0	99.9	Stable
PMS-9	113	79.0	86.2	100.0	Unstable
PMS-10	107	69.5	100.0	100.0	Stable

days to 50% flowering, plant height, percent pollen sterility, and percent spikelet fertility, for which we used the mean of 25 panicles.

We identified several stable CMS lines with varying duration and plant type (see table). V20 A, IR58025 A, PMS-1 A, PMS-2 A, PMS-5 A, PMS-8 A, and PMS-10 A had complete pollen sterility and almost 100% spikelet sterility. In

contrast with earlier observations, IR62829 A had slight fertility of pollen and spikelets, possibly because of a different seed source.

These stable lines all had very short stature (63.6-72.6 cm), except IR58025 A, which had semidwarf stature (81.0 cm). V20 A had early duration, IR58025 A and PMS-2 mid-early, and others, medium to mid-late. Observations at